

The adaptation of former Coal power plants infrastructure and terrain into the new hydrogen-focused standard in the region of León, Spain.

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Abstract:

Since the Spanish energy sector was partially privatized by the government under the presidency of Felipe González and later reassured by Jose María Aznar, Spain has suffered from abrupt changes in the control and maintenance of its electric grid. Due to this mass privatization intended to improve the overall infrastructure, the price of the energy for the final users has been at the top for Spain in the European Rankings in a country where the average income is 20.2% lower than the European average. This paper aims to analyze how good are the new decarbonization measures imposed by the European Union and the Spanish government in terms of making good use of the existing infrastructure and the new technologies flooding both the market and academia headlines, and from all of those, we will analyze how the new hydrogen-oriented proposals will impact on the Leonese region.

1. Introduction and framework.

Spain may be known for its good weather and the huge solar-panel-covered surface displayed across the country, but besides its good planning, and outside any environmental agenda, Spain still heavily relies on non-renewable energies, even when the Installed power capacity on the Iberian Peninsula, as of 31st December 2021 reached 57.4% of renewable energy [1], and it has been increasing ever since, last year we achieved a more humble, yet not bad 42,2 % of our generation from renewable sources, 4% less than the previous year [2].

This proves that for any desired quota of clean energy we want to achieve, the installed capacity of this one need to exceed by quite a decent margin the real energy outcome we are getting from it, given the non-continuous nature of natural sources.

To solve this inequality between generation and demand, some studies, like the one performed by *Matthew D. Leonard* [3], suggest that hydrogen is one, if not the only, way we can store this energy safely and efficiently for us to use when the base generation can't fulfill the demand.

Spain seems to be a good environment for these kinds of systems given both its geographical situation and its weather, having organisms like the *International Energy Agency* stated that "It will be important to adapt the policy and regulatory framework, where needed, to gradually shape such a new integrated energy system." And recommended the government to implement a 'National Adaptation Plan for the energy sector' to palliate some of the impacts of climate change. [4]

As we can see in the following figure, courtesy of *Mordor Intelligence* and *BP*, Spain's generation baseline might appear to be covered entirely by renewable energy, but given the previously mentioned intermittent nature of these methods, other energy sources must be engaged during a day in order to meet energy market's demand, while some of the energy generated by clean sources will be unavoidably lost during a day for not having enough demand of it.

Electricity Generation, by Source, in %, Spain, 2020

Source: BP Statistical Review

Figure 1: Energy generation source ratio. [5]

To refute any bias related to the COVID19 pandemic, the graph referring to the generation of the past July 1st, 2023 at 3:00 AM, is shown below.

Figure 2: Energy generation source ratio on July 1st, 2023. This figure includes the Canary and Balearic Islands, as well as Ceuta and Melilla, hence the existence of Diesel Generators. 3:00AM time mark is the preset on the website when no other time is selected

Figure 3: Further analysis on the Energy generation source ratio on July 1st, 2023. [6]

As we can see in the figure above, the problem with relying fully on renewable energy shows its true colors. Of course, this just a one-day-analysis but this behavior it's expected to replicate itself along the year with slightly different peaks, numbers, and generation ratios, depending on the season. This analysis shows that the peak demand took place at around 22:00 and due to the insufficiency of "green energy" by that time, traditional generation methods needed to be engaged in order to meet the demand, while later that night, at around 00:25, we had a surplus of renewable energy that either has to be sold to neighbor countries or stored somehow, and this last option is what is motivating most of the research and current industry, hence the very existence of this document.

2. Spain's energy context.

Spain's main electric grid is managed by *Red Eléctrica de España* (REE in the following references), a partly state-owned and public limited Spanish corporation which is responsible of maintaining, developing, and extending the grid, managing the transmission of electricity between external systems and the peninsula, and guaranteeing third party access to the transmission grid under equal conditions.

Transmission grids are the ones between the main generators and the regional substations managed by the distributors. This transmission grid is supposed to cover the transport of energy among the distant locations in which the generators are and the areas nearby population cores.

On this matter, the Spanish electric infrastructure has done a great job connecting various regions between each other, especially considering that some regions of Spain have been totally abandoned for years now [7], making maintenance and demand predictions difficult for the electric operators and main distributors.

Figure 4: Geographic representation of peninsula's main transmission lines in 2008 [8]

The previous map, although outdated, represents the incredible electrical extension of the Spanish territory (not including the islands and the territories in Africa), and does a good job representing those major population cores that have been discussed before and where, for census reasons, there is a much higher electrical demand.

On the other hand, we have the distribution grids, managed by the five distributors conforming the energy oligopoly.

Figure 5: Geographical distribution of Spain's energy distributors. [5]

As we can see in the map, the State of Castilla and León, the object of this study, has its territory covered by facilities from three

different distribution companies. These companies own different generation plants and distribution lines in different locations across the region, each one with their own decarbonization plans to meet the new renewable energy standard we talked about before.

3. The Leonese Region and its energy resources.

Coal mineral began to be used in England since the 11th century and was key for the Industrial Revolution of the 18th century. In Spain, the development of coal mining was delayed until the late 19th and early 20th centuries, due to the import of foreign coal and the lack of industry. In Castilla y León, the mines in the north of León and Palencia were linked to the railway and the Basque steel industry, and in El Bierzo thermal power plants were built that demanded anthracite. Coal has been a source of wealth and employment in these regions, and still plays an important role in the national energy supply.

In the 20th century, coal mining in Spain reached its maximum development during Franco's autarky, when national production was encouraged to reduce dependence on foreign sources [9]. However, from the 1960s onwards, with the opening to the outside world and the increase of competition, a reconversion process began that led to the closure of many mines. In recent decades, the sector has suffered a deep crisis due to the competition of other fossil fuels that are cheaper and cleaner, as well as environmental policies that seek to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Despite this, coal remains an important source of energy in Spain and in the world.

Coal used to be the main generation method in the region, along with hydro-electric, for more than a century [10]. As per 2008, the region had a total capacity of around 50000 MW of non-renewable energies coming from coal, combined cycles, gas and nuclear. [8]

coal industry has been declining since the late 1990s, driven by external economic factors, domestic policies, and European Union mandates. Coal mine employment has shrunk from 45,000 in 1990 to about 1,700 today. The share of coal in Spain's power generation fell from 40% in 1990 to 5% in 2019. The economic reconversion that affected the Leonese mining basin and Palencia's mining basin during the 1980s and 1990s resulted in the closure of numerous mines, social impoverishment, with a sharp increase of unemployment and the beginning of a new migratory movement towards other Spanish regions.

The Burgos Provincial Energy Agency was created to promote renewable energies and energy efficiency. The Spanish government has committed at least USD 2.11 billion to oil and gas, but no public money commitments have been identified for coal. The Spanish government has set a target of 74% renewable energy in the electricity mix by 2030 which will be met by relying on the hydro-electric energy potential available in the region, although hydropower is a significant source of renewable energy in Spain, in 2022, in Castilla y León, we generated approximately 4,420 gigawatt-hours of hydropower, becoming the region with the highest generation of this type of renewable energy in Spain. [11] In 2020, Castilla y León produced 8,027 GWh of hydropower, accounting for 26.2% of the national total. [12]

As for the province of León, during 2009, hydropower plants produced 895,465 MWh of energy [13] which shows the great improvement in this energy generation method during these last years which has allowed the region to produce up to 25,7% of its total energy outcome from Hydroelectric power plants [14].

Figure 6: Castilla y León leading the national ranking on hydro-power generation (2022). [11]

Figure 7: Castilla y León Map in which we can see the main location of Hydropower and coal plants. [13]

Despite hydroelectric and coal power having been the main energy providers in Castilla y León for centuries, the closure of the mines that we have already discussed forced the past and current government to reinvent its generation system and implement more energy renewable. The most notable for this region currently is, by a large margin, wind power [15].

According to some national sources [14], Castilla and León is the biggest clean-energy producer in the country, being 87% of its energy consumption renewable and 49,4% of this last one produced by wind power. In the 2020 only, the installed power coming from clean sources increased by a 24.5% with respect 2019 [2].

4. Alternatives to the coal mine closure and relative activities in energy generation for the Leonese region

As we have discussed, the mining industry in the region has decreased drastically, being now reserved mainly for residual coal uses and other materials like mercury or wolframium [16], so regional government has been working on providing a fair alternative for such a big economy switch, to the point that the central government is promoting some initiatives to palliate this

huge change in region's economy and workforce.[17],[18], [4, p. 157], [19].

This factors, along with some other well-known discouragements about some renewable energies have led to people to believe that this rather rushed implementation of climate-focused-measures is not only detrimental to economy and job keeping, as stated before, but also brings some other debatable points to the table. Again let's bring back our attention to *Matthew D. Leonard's* article [3] in which we can find some of this problems:

- A. The inflexibility of base-load steam power plants: Shutting down and starting up these plants frequently reduces their thermal efficiency and can cause damage to their equipment. Additionally, some types of power plants, such as nuclear power plants, require a significant amount of time to produce full power starting from a cold state.
- B. Difficulty in controlling and adjusting electricity demand: While incentives can be offered to adjust electricity demand during high production hours from renewables, full control of electric power demand is impossible to achieve. This is particularly challenging for wind energy, which is more variable than solar energy.
- C. Lack of utility-level storage capacity: Investing in storage capacity that can store excess power produced during high production hours and seasons is necessary. This would enable the use of stored power during peak demand periods. However, the implementation of utility-level storage requires significant investment.
- D. Cost implications: Substituting coal and nuclear power plants with other units, such as gas turbines, requires substantial investment, making electricity significantly more expensive. Additionally, the production of hydrogen through electrolysis for storage purposes adds to the cost.
- E. Dissipation of excess power: When the contribution of renewable energy exceeds 25% of the annual energy produced and consumed in a region, there are periods when the power demanded by the rest of the power plants becomes negative. This means that some of the produced power must be dissipated and wasted.

To *Juan Ignacio de la Fuente* in his article [20], The implementation of green hydrogen in Spain presents several challenges that must be addressed in order to achieve the ambitious goals set by the government. One of the main challenges is the need for a large amount of renewable energy in excess not injected into the grid. This implies building and installing about 12 GW of additional renewable power by 2030 just to produce green hydrogen.

Another challenge is the difficulty of finding available land, obtaining environmental and social permits, and having enough construction companies to carry out renewable projects within the planned timeframe. In addition, there is the demand for deionized or demineralized water for the electrolysis process, which requires about 11 liters per kilogram of green hydrogen produced. This implies considerable water consumption and residual water rejection that must be properly managed.

Furthermore, there is competition with other uses and purposes of renewable energy, such as decarbonizing the national hydrogen industry itself or electrifying land transport. These could have priority over exporting green biofuels to other countries or sectors.

Finally, there is the complexity of capturing and storing the CO2 necessary for the synthesis process of green methanol. This

requires developing and implementing efficient and safe carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies.

In conclusion, while the implementation of green hydrogen in Spain presents several challenges, it also offers great opportunities for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and transitioning towards a more sustainable energy system. In fact According to an article [21], the regional board will establish three green hydrogen development zones in Castilla and León, in addition to supporting an existing project in *La Robla*. The projects will be located in:

- *El Bierzo* and the north of *León*, with initiatives linked to a just energy transition and the production and evacuation of green hydrogen from the port of *Gijón* to *Rotterdam*.
- An axis associated with *La Mudarra*, which includes areas of *Valladolid*, *Salamanca* and *Zamora*, with great renewable power and ease of transport by pipeline and road.
- A strip between *Burgos* and *Soria*, with renewable power, industry associated with hydrogen and pipeline and land exit.

These projects are considered “hydrogen valleys” by the European Commission and the participation of universities and technological centers in the region in R&D&I on energy will be promoted.

These projects give some hope of becoming true on some of the big claims from *Naturgy*, one of the main Distributors that we talked about previously. *Naturgy* plans on opening up to 38 new hydrogen facilities before 2025 [22].

This big implication from corporate entities as big as *Naturgy* or some projects like the “Hydrogen Corridor” that *Cepsa* plans to open between *Algeciras* and *Rotterdam*[23], will certainly be crucial for the development of some other projects that will be driven in the region, like the ones presented by the Board of *Castille and León* such as continuous energy generation combining renewable sources, the incorporation of vehicles with fuel cells in selected niche markets, domestic cogeneration with fuel cell technology, the development of reformers for the production of hydrogen from fossil fuels, the research on new designs, materials and technologies for PEM fuel cells, the energy storage based on hydrogen to defer wind production and the establishment of new safety standards for the use of hydrogen sensors. Some other entities such as *CIDAUT*, *INTA*, *CSIC*, *AICIA*, *BESEL*, *CARTIF*, *CIEMAT*, *CARBUROS METÁLICOS*, *ENERMAN*, *PYGSUR*, *ADE*, *JRC* and *David Fuel Cell Components* will be directly involved in these last proposals [24].

Figure 8: Map of new Hydrogen (blue) and Gas (Green) pipes planned by 2040. [25]

5. Conclusion:

Even though there is some indicatives that all these projects are going to be done sooner or later, judging by the huge amount of resources that companies are willing to invest in them. There is almost no information available yet about where and how these projects are going to be conducted exactly.

Judging by all the marketing involved around the topic of hydrogen in Spain, I would say that a lot of the things that are being proposed and published in journals and mainstream media are yet another kind of political propaganda that aims to side with a specific profile of voter.

There is no doubt that our future depends on implementing reliable and efficient methods of generating power in a renewable way, but if we just refer ourselves to the raw data showed in the platforms referred in the introduction of the document, we will see that we still heavily rely on non-renewable energy sources. This is not bad perse, but just an easy and fast way of generating energy in demand peaks that we can not supply solely by renewable energies.

I would also like to add that the mystification around nuclear energy seems to be affecting more and more countries in both Europe and outside Europe, which defeats the purpose of looking for a safe and reliable source of energy that we can use as a generation baseline. Our goal as an increasingly technical society is to avoid falling in judgmental biases about technology itself and using it wisely to achieve our major goals. We need to see both Hydrogen and Carbon merely as energy vectors that we, as humans have the ability to mutate and use in accordance with our needs and respecting our environment, outside any political and philosophical ideas.

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